

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 2 | APRIL - JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

APOLLO MARR F. BUGAY, PH.D. RPsy

Instructor 1

Negros Oriental State University

apollo.bugay@norsu.edu.ph

“APPLYING COGNITIVE BEHAVIOR THERAPY IN RURAL HIGHER EDUCATION COMMUNITIES”

Cognitive Behavior Therapy (CBT) is a form of talk therapy developed by Dr. Aaron Beck in the 1960s that focuses on addressing unhelpful patterns of thinking resulting in maladaptive behavior (APA Div. 12, 2016). It has been proven to be an effective treatment in multiple psychological cases such as major depression, anxiety disorders, and in suicide prevention.

Being a guidance coordinator and a registered psychologist at a State University in an external campus located in a rural community, I have devoted time and effort to studying CBT to support students who suffer from mental health problems. Students often present academic, financial, and family problems that negatively affect their well-being. I have observed that using strategies such as Socratic questioning, mindfulness, character strengths, and psycho-education from CBT has helped my students tremendously. What I liked the most about CBT is its view that clients can be empowered, that they are capable of positive change. They are not helpless but have the potential to use their inner strengths to solve their problems. Furthermore, what makes CBT more effective is its use of action plans. CBT affirms that its effectiveness is not just in the counseling session, but the application of the concepts in between sessions through action plans.

As much as CBT is effective, there are challenges such as the Manila-centricity of experts and trainers. Being a mental health practitioner in the province has its challenges, such as the inaccessibility of training. Although online training modes exist, many certification programs are only available in Metro Manila.

Overall, Cognitive Behavior Therapy is an effective psychotherapeutic approach in dealing with people's mental health problems. It has been found effective in multiple cases of maladaptive behavior. There is anecdotal evidence supporting its effectiveness among mental health practitioners in higher education institutions in rural communities. On the other hand, the accessibility of training for mental health practitioners in rural communities using this technique is difficult. Yet there is hope with adequate government support for the training of mental health practitioners in urban or rural communities. Cognitive Behavior Therapy will be a good tool for helping individuals with mental health problems.

REFERENCES

APA Div. 12 Society of Clinical Psychology. (2016). What is Cognitive Behavior Therapy? American Psychological Association. Retrieved April 27, 2025, from <https://www.apa.org/ptsd-guideline/patients-and-families/cognitive-behavioral>